

The symmetric solutions for three-point singular boundary value problems of differential equation

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Abstract—In this paper, by constructing a special operator and using fixed point index theorem of cone, we get the sufficient conditions for symmetric positive solution of a class of nonlinear singular boundary value problems with p-Laplace operator, which improved and generalized the result of related paper.

Keywords—Banach space, cone, fixed point index, singular differential equation, p-Laplace operator, symmetric solutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE boundary value problems with p-Laplace operator arises in a variety of applied mathematics and physics, and they are widely applied in studying for non-newtonian fluid mechanics, cosmological physics, plasma physics, and theory of elasticity, etc. In recent years, some important results have been obtained by a variety of method(see[1-4]). On the other hand, the study for the symmetric and multiple solutions to this problem is more and more active (see[5-6]). In paper [5], Sun study for the problem

$$\begin{cases} (u)'' + a(t)f(t, u(t)) = 0, t \in (0, 1) \\ u(0) = \alpha u(\eta) = u(1), \end{cases}$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1), \eta \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, by using spectrum theory, Sun get the existence of symmetric and multiple solution. But when $p \neq 2$, $\phi_p(u)$ is nonlinear, so the method of the paper [5] is not suitable to p-laplace operator. In paper [6], Tian and Liu study for the problem

$$\begin{cases} (\phi_p(u'))' + a(t)f(t, u(t)) = 0, t \in (0, 1) \\ u(0) = \alpha u(\eta) = u(1), \end{cases}$$

where $\phi(s)$ is p-Laplace operator. Motivated by paper [5,6], we consider the existence of solution for the following problems:

$$\begin{cases} (\phi_p(u'))' + h_1(t)f(u, v) = 0, \\ (\phi_p(v'))' + h_2(t)g(u) = 0, \\ u(0) = \gamma u(\eta) = u(1), \\ v(0) = \gamma v(\eta) = v(1), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $t \in (0, 1), \gamma \in (0, 1), \eta \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, $\phi(s)$ is a p-Laplace operator, i.e. $\phi_p(s) = |s|^{p-2}s, p > 1$. Obviously, if $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then $(\phi_p)^{-1} = \phi_q$.

Compare with above paper, our method is different. By constructing a new operator, and using fixed point index theorem, we get the sufficient condition of the existence of symmetric solution, which improved and generalized the result of paper [5,6,7].

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In this paper, we always suppose that the following conditions hold:

(H₁) $f \in C([0, +\infty) \times [0, +\infty), [0, +\infty)), g \in C([0, +\infty), [0, +\infty))$.

(H₂) $h_i \in C((0, 1), [0, +\infty)), h_i(t) = h_i(1-t), t \in (0, 1)$, for any subinterval of $(0, 1)$, $h_i(t) \not\equiv 0$, and $\int_0^1 h_i(t)dt < +\infty (i = 1, 2)$.

(H₃) There exists $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, such that $\liminf_{u \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{g(u)}{u^{\frac{p-1}{\alpha}}} = +\infty$ and $\liminf_{v \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{f(u, v)}{v^{(p-1)\alpha}} > 0$ hold uniformly to $u \in R^+$.

(H₄) There exists $\beta \in (0, +\infty)$, such that $\limsup_{u \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{g(u)}{u^{\frac{p-1}{\beta}}} = 0$ and $\limsup_{v \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{f(u, v)}{v^{(p-1)\beta}} < +\infty$ hold uniformly to $u \in R^+$.

(H₅) There exists $n \in (0, 1)$, such that $\liminf_{u \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{g(u)}{u^{\frac{p-1}{n}}} = +\infty$ and $\liminf_{v \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{f(u, v)}{v^{(p-1)n}} > 0$ hold uniformly to $u \in R^+$.

(H₆) $f(u, v)$ and $g(u)$ are nondecreasing with respect to u and v , and there exists $R > 0$, such that $\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q(k_1(s))ds f(R, \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q(k_1(s))ds \times g(R)) < R$, where $k_i(s) = \int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_i(\tau)d\tau, i = 1, 2$.

For convenience, we list the following definitions and lemmas:

Definition 1.1 If $u(t) = u(1-t), t \in [0, 1]$, we call $u(t)$ is symmetric in $[0, 1]$.

Definition 1.2 If (u, v) is a positive solution of problem (1), and u, v is symmetric in $[0, 1]$, we call (u, v) is symmetric positive solution of problem (1).

Definition 1.3 If $u(\lambda t_1 + (1-\lambda)t_2) \geq \lambda u(t_1) + (1-\lambda)u(t_2)$, we call $u(t)$ is concave in $[0, 1]$.

Let $E = C[0, 1]$, define the norm $\|u\| = \max_{t \in [0, 1]} |u(t)|$, obviously $(E, \|\cdot\|)$ is a Banach space.

Let $K = \{u \in E | u(t) > 0, u(t) \text{ is a symmetric concave function}, t \in [0, 1]\}$, then K is a cone in E . By (H₁), (H₂), the solution of problem (1) is equivalent to the solution of system of equation (2).

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 u(t) &= \begin{cases} \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ \int_t^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases} \\
 v(t) &= \begin{cases} \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ \int_t^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

We define $T : K \rightarrow E$:

$$(Tu)(t) = \begin{cases} \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ \int_t^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \\ \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ \int_t^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Obviously $Tu \in E$, it is easy to show if T has fixed point u , then by (4), problem (1) has a solution (u, v) .

Lemma 1.1 Let $(H_1), (H_2)$, then $T : K \rightarrow K$ is completely continuous.

Proof $\forall u \in K$, by $(H_1), (H_2)$, we can get $(Tu)(t) \geq 0, t \in [0, 1]$.

$$v'(t) = \begin{cases} \phi_q \left(\int_t^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right), 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ -\phi_q \left(\int_t^1 h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right), \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases}$$

correspondingly $(\phi_p(v'))' = -h_2(t)g(u) \leq 0, 0 < t < 1$, so v is concave in $[0, 1]$.

Next we show v is symmetric in $[0, 1]$.

When $t \in [0, \frac{1}{2}], 1-t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, so

$$\begin{aligned}
 v(1-t) &= \int_{1-t}^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ &\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &= \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ &\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &= v(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have $v(1-t) = v(t), t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$. So v is a symmetric concave function in $[0, 1]$.

$$(Tu)'(t) = \begin{cases} \phi_q \left(\int_t^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right), 0 \leq t \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ -\phi_q \left(\int_t^1 h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right), \frac{1}{2} \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases}$$

(2) so $(\phi_p((Tu)'))' = -h_1(t)f(u, v) \leq 0, 0 < t < 1$, i.e. Tu is concave in $[0, 1]$.

Next we show Tu is symmetric in $[0, 1]$. when $t \in [0, \frac{1}{2}], 1-t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, so

$$\begin{aligned}
 (Tu)(1-t) &= \int_{1-t}^1 \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ &\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &= \int_0^t \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ &\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &= (Tu)(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have $(Tu)(1-t) = (Tu)(t), t \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$. so Tu is concave in $[0, 1]$, so $TK \subset K$. On the other hand, let D is a arbitrary bounded set of K , then there exist constant $c > 0$, such that $D \subset \{u \in K \mid \|u\| \leq c\}$. Let $b = \max_{u \in [0, c]} g(u)$, so $\forall u \in D$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|v\| &= \left| \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \right. \\ &\left. \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \frac{b^{q-1}}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) d\tau \right) ds = a.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $L = \max_{u \in [0, c], v \in [0, a]} f(u, v)$, so $\forall u \in D$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|Tu\| &= \left| \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \right| \\ &\leq \frac{L^{q-1}}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|(Tu)'\| &= \max\{|\phi_q(\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)f(u(\tau), v(\tau))d\tau)|, \\ &|\phi_q(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 h_1(\tau)f(u(\tau), v(\tau))d\tau)|\} \\ &\leq L^{q-1}\phi_q(\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau). \end{aligned}$$

By Arzela-Ascoli theorem, we know TD is compact set. By Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem, it is easy to show T is continuous in K , so $T : K \rightarrow K$ is completely continuous.

Lemma 1.2 For any $0 < \epsilon < \frac{1}{2}$, $u \in K$, we have

- (1) $u(t) \geq \|u\|t(1-t), \forall t \in [0, 1]$;
- (2) $u(t) \geq \epsilon^2\|u\|, t \in [\epsilon, 1-\epsilon]$. (the proof is elementary, we omit it.)

Lemma 1.3(see [8]) Let K is a cone of E in Banach space, Ω_1 and Ω_2 are open subsets in E , $\theta \in \Omega_1, \overline{\Omega_1} \subset \Omega_2$, and $T : K \cap (\overline{\Omega_2} \setminus \Omega_1) \rightarrow K$ is a completely continuous operator, and satisfy one of the following conditions:

- (1) $\|Tx\| \leq \|x\|, \forall x \in K \cap \partial\Omega_1, \|Tx\| \geq x, \forall x \in K \cap \partial\Omega_2$,
 - (2) $\|Tx\| \geq \|x\|, \forall x \in K \cap \partial\Omega_1, \|Tx\| \leq x, \forall x \in K \cap \partial\Omega_2$,
- then A has at least one fixed point in $K \cap (\Omega_2 \setminus \Omega_1)$.

Lemma 1.4(see [9]) Let K is a cone of E in Banach space, $K_r = \{x \in K \mid \|x\| \leq r\}$, suppose $A : K_r \rightarrow K$ is a completely continuous, and satisfy $Tx \neq x, \forall x \in \partial K_r$,

- (1) If $\|Tx\| \leq x, \forall x \in \partial K_r$, then $i(T, K_r, K) = 1$,
- (2) If $\|Tx\| \geq x, \forall x \in \partial K_r$, then $i(T, K_r, K) = 0$.

II. CONCLUSION

Theorem 2.1 Suppose $(H_1) - (H_4)$ hold, then problem (1) has at least one positive solution.

Proof By (H_3) , there exist ν and a sufficient large number $M > 0$, such that

$$f(u, v) \geq \nu^{p-1}v^{(p-1)\alpha}, \forall u \in R^+, v > M, \quad (5)$$

$$g(u) \geq C_0^{p-1}u^{\frac{p-1}{\alpha}}, \forall u > M, \quad (6)$$

where $C_0 = \max\{(\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(k_2(s))ds)^{-1}, (\frac{2}{\nu\gamma\epsilon^2(\frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(k_1(s))^{\alpha+1}})^{\frac{1}{\alpha}})\}$. Let $N = (M+1)\epsilon^{-2}$, if $u \in K \cap \partial K_N$, by Lemma 2, $\min_{\epsilon \leq t \leq 1-\epsilon} u(t) \geq \epsilon^2\|u\| = \epsilon^2N = M+1$, by (3)-(6) and the symmetric property, for any $t \in [\epsilon, 1-\epsilon]$

$$\begin{aligned} v(t) &= \int_0^t \phi_q(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^s h_2(\tau)g(u(\tau))d\tau)ds + \\ &\quad \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)g(u(\tau))d\tau)ds \\ &\geq \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)g(u(\tau))d\tau)ds \\ &\geq \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)g(u(\tau))d\tau)ds \\ &\geq \frac{C_0\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)(u(\tau))^{\frac{p-1}{\alpha}}d\tau)ds \\ &\geq \frac{C_0\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)d\tau)ds(\epsilon^2\|u\|)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ &\geq \frac{C_0\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau)d\tau)ds(M+1)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ &\geq M+1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|Tu\| &= |\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)f(u(\tau), v(\tau))d\tau)ds + \\ &\quad \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)f(u(\tau), v(\tau))d\tau)ds,| \\ &\geq \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)f(u(\tau), v(\tau))d\tau)ds, \\ &\geq \frac{\nu}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)v(\tau)^{(p-1)\alpha}d\tau)ds, \\ &\geq \frac{\nu}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau)ds \times \\ &\quad (\frac{C_0\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_{\epsilon}^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau)ds)^{\alpha} \epsilon^2\|u\| \\ &= \nu C_0^{\alpha} \gamma^{\alpha} \epsilon^2 (\frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\eta} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau)ds)^{\alpha+1} \|u\| \\ &\geq 2\|u\|, \end{aligned}$$

so $\|Tu\| > \|u\|, \forall u \in K \cap K_N$, by lemma 1.4, we can get

$$i(T, K \cap K_N, K) = 0. \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, by the second limit of H_4 , there exists a sufficient small number $r_1 \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$C_1^{p-1} = \sup\{\frac{f(u, v)}{v^{(p-1)\beta}} \mid u \in R^+, v \in (0, r_1)\} < +\infty. \quad (8)$$

Let $\epsilon = \min\{\frac{r_1(1-\gamma)}{\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau)ds}, (\frac{C_1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau)d\tau)ds)^{\frac{-\beta-1}{\beta}}\}$, by the first limit of H_4 , there exist a sufficient small number $r_2 \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$g(u) \leq \epsilon^{p-1}u^{\frac{p-1}{\beta}}, \forall u \in [0, r_2]. \quad (9)$$

Take $r = \min\{r_1, r_2\}$, by (9), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} v(t) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^s h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \\ &\quad \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &\leq \frac{\epsilon}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \|u\|^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &\leq r_1^{1+\frac{1}{p}} < r_1, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_r, s \in [0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

By (8), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \|Tu\| &\leq \left| \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds, \right| \\ &\leq \frac{C_1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \times \\ &\quad \left(\frac{\epsilon}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \right)^\beta \|u\| \\ &= C_1 \epsilon^\beta \left(\frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \right)^{\beta+1} \|u\| \\ &\leq \|u\|, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_r, t \in [0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

So $\|Tu\| \leq \|u\|, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_r$, by lemma 1.4, we get

$$i(T, K \cap K_r, K) = 1. \quad (10)$$

By lemma 1.5, T has at least one fixed point in $K \cap (\overline{K_N} \setminus K_r)$, so problem (1) has at least a system positive solution.

Theorem 2.2 Suppose $(H_1), (H_2), (H_3), (H_5), (H_6)$ hold, then problem (1) has at least two systems positive solutions.

Proof By (H_5) , there exists $\mu > 0$ and a sufficient small number $\xi \in (0, 1)$, such that

$$f(u, v) \geq \mu^{p-1} v^{n(p-1)}, \forall u \in R^+, 0 \leq v \leq \xi, \quad (11)$$

$$g(u) \geq (C_2 u)^{\frac{p-1}{n}}, \forall 0 \leq u \leq \xi, \quad (12)$$

where

$$C_2 = 2 \left(\frac{\mu \epsilon^2}{1-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \right)^n \int_\epsilon^\eta \phi_q(k_1(s)) ds \int_\epsilon^\eta (\phi_q(k_2(s)))^n ds \right)^{-1}$$

since $g \in C(R^+, R^+)$, $g(0) \equiv 0$, so there exists $\sigma \in (0, \xi)$ such that $\forall u \in [0, \sigma]$, we have

$$g(u) \leq \left(\frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \right)^{-1},$$

this imply

$$\begin{aligned} v(t) &\leq \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &\leq \xi, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_\sigma. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

By using Jensen inequality, $0 < q \leq 1$, and (11)-(13), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} (Tu)\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) &\geq \frac{\mu}{1-\gamma} \int_\epsilon^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \times \\ &\quad \left(\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_\epsilon^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \right)^n \\ &\geq \frac{\mu}{1-\gamma} \int_\epsilon^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \times \\ &\quad \left(\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \right)^n \int_\epsilon^\eta (\phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) g(u(\tau)) d\tau \right))^n ds \\ &\geq \frac{\mu C_2 \epsilon^2}{1-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \right)^n \int_\epsilon^\eta \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \times \\ &\quad \int_\epsilon^\eta (\phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_2(\tau) d\tau \right))^n ds \|u\| \\ &= 2 \|u\|, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_\sigma. \end{aligned}$$

So $\|Tu\| > \|u\|, \forall u \in K \cap \partial K_\sigma$, by lemma 1.4, we can get

$$i(T, K \cap K_\sigma, K) = 0. \quad (14)$$

We can choose $N > R > \sigma$, such that (7),(14) hold together. On the other hand by (3),(4) and H_6 we can get

$$\begin{aligned} (Tu)(t) &< \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) f(u(\tau), v(\tau)) d\tau \right) ds \\ &\leq \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds \times \\ &\quad f\left(R, \frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \phi_q \left(\int_s^{\frac{1}{2}} h_1(\tau) d\tau \right) ds g(R)\right) \\ &< R, \forall u \in K \cap K_R, \forall t \in [0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

So for any $u \in K \cap K_R$, by lemma 1.4, we can get

$$i(T, K \cap K_R, K) = 1. \quad (15)$$

By (7),(14),(15), we have

$$\begin{aligned} &i(T, K \cap (K_N \setminus \overline{K_R}), K) \\ &= i(T, K \cap K_N, K) - i(T, K \cap K_R, K) \\ &= -1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &i(T, K \cap (K_R \setminus \overline{K_\sigma}), K) \\ &= i(T, K \cap K_R, K) - i(T, K \cap K_\sigma, K) \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

So T have at least two fixed points in $K \cap (K_N \setminus \overline{K_R})$ and $K \cap (K_R \setminus \overline{K_\sigma})$, by (4), problem (1) has at least two system solutions.

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